

SYMPTOMS AND TYPES OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE DISEASE, HEART ISCHEMIA

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Abstract: Ischemic heart disease or cardiac ischemia is a chronic or acute disorder of the blood supply to the myocardium (the muscle layer of the heart). This condition is caused by an insufficient supply of oxygen to the heart. This occurs when arterial blood is supplied to the heart muscle in limited quantities due to damage to the coronary arteries. The acute form of ischemic heart disease is myocardial infarction, the chronic form is angina pectoris.

Keywords: Cardiovascular diseases, ischemic heart, risk factors

Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death in many developed countries. In recent years, there has been a trend towards a decrease in mortality from this cause. Since 2015, the mortality rate from cardiovascular diseases has accounted for less than half of all deaths and continues to increase.

However, this figure is still higher than in European countries. Despite the fact that diseases of the circulatory system are the leading cause of death in all developed countries of the world, the mortality rate from cardiovascular diseases in the European Union is significantly lower than in Russia, where in 2015 this figure was 36.7%.

Among circulatory system diseases, ischemic heart disease stands out, which causes more than half of all deaths from cardiovascular diseases. According to statistics, in 2018, ischemic heart disease caused 53% of deaths from circulatory system diseases - this was 24% of the total number of deaths (in 3% of cases, deaths were due to myocardial infarction).

Causes of coronary heart disease. The most common cause of narrowing of blood vessels is the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, which are formed due to the accumulation of fat on the walls of blood vessels. Therefore, the risk group includes people who have a number of conditions for the accumulation of cholesterol in the blood vessels: smokers, alcohol abusers, people with diabetes and obesity, and those with a genetic predisposition to hyperlipidemia.

The first symptoms of ischemic heart disease: Shortness of breath. This condition can occur both during brisk walking or climbing stairs, and during calm movements. •Arrhythmia. Interruptions in the work of the heart, rapid heartbeat. •Hypertension. Sharp jumps and rises in blood pressure. •Pressure angina. Pressure pain located behind the chest, radiating to the neck and left shoulder. •Myocardial infarction. This is similar to an attack of angina, but is not controlled by medication. It is accompanied by severe pain in the heart area. It indicates the development of coronary artery disease. It is considered life-threatening in itself due to damage to the heart muscle.

Ischemic heart disease can manifest itself even in people who do not have obvious risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, it is important to know the symptoms of coronary artery disease. The sooner the circulatory disorder is detected, the higher the chances of successful treatment. At the same time, the development of ischemic heart disease often proceeds slowly and in the early stages is almost asymptomatic (rarely

does a person pay attention to pain in the heart area and slight shortness of breath). In order to detect the disease at an early stage, it is necessary to undergo regular preventive examinations by a cardiologist and therapist.

Types of ischemic heart disease. Treatment depends on the type of ischemic disease. There are several forms of ischemic heart disease that must be identified during diagnosis: Sudden coronary death. Primary cardiac arrest caused not by myocardial infarction, but by electrical instability of the myocardium. However, this condition does not always lead to death, and sometimes successful resuscitation measures can be taken.

Angina pectoris. Angina pectoris, in turn, is divided into several subtypes: stable and unstable angina (new-onset, early stage of infarction or progressive), vasoplastic and coronary syndrome X. Myocardial infarction. During a heart attack, necrosis of heart tissue occurs due to insufficient or absent blood supply. It can lead to cardiac arrest. Postinfarction cardiosclerosis. It develops as a result of myocardial infarction, when necrotic fibers of the heart muscle are replaced by connective tissue. At the same time, the tissue is unable to contract, which leads to chronic heart failure. Heart failure or circulatory failure. The name of the disease speaks for itself - this form indicates that the coronary arteries do not receive enough oxygenated blood.

Heart failure or circulatory failure. The name of the disease speaks for itself - this form indicates that the coronary arteries do not receive enough oxygenated blood. Prevention of heart disease. Everyone knows that any disease is easier to prevent than to treat. Therefore, one should not neglect preventive measures to maintain the health of blood vessels and arteries. First of all, a person should eliminate the obvious risk factors for coronary heart disease: quit smoking, reduce alcohol consumption to a minimum, give up fatty foods and foods high in cholesterol. It is also necessary to pay attention to physical activity (especially cardio exercises - walking, cycling, dancing, swimming). This will help not only to lose weight, but also to strengthen the walls of blood vessels. Every six months you need to get a blood test to control sugar and cholesterol levels.

Hair loss. It's hard to believe, but premature hair loss in both men and women is actually linked to a higher risk of clogged arteries and blood clots. For example, a study of 37,000 men found a link between hair loss and cardiovascular disease. Another study of more than 4,000 women found that women are also affected by this condition. Therefore, if you're experiencing more hair loss than usual, it's a good idea to get checked out by a cardiologist.

Ear creases. Another sign of coronary heart disease is a crease or fold in the ear canal. This sign of the disease has been noted in many studies conducted in recent decades. Doctors say that the main thing is the deterioration of the blood supply: due to blockage of the arteries, blood does not pump well and the body tries to supply oxygen to the vital organs first, while it becomes difficult for oxygen to reach the rest of the organs.

Pain in the legs. It is especially important for smokers to pay attention to this symptom: due to poor blood supply, the arteries of the lower extremities become clogged, and acute pain in the legs can lead to limping or falling. If this happens, you should see a doctor, and also try to eat more vegetables and walk.

Neck and jaw pain. This is a very important symptom that every woman should know: the truth is that one of the first signs of a heart attack in women is not chest pain, but neck or jaw pain. Unfortunately, this is why women often go to the doctor too late, because they do not

even suspect a heart attack. It is important to remember that neck or jaw pain is an important reason to contact a cardiologist.

Back pain. Another unusual but very common symptom of ischemic heart disease is back pain. The fact is that poor blood circulation can weaken the discs and increase pressure on the spine, resulting in back pain. If you experience frequent back pain, it is advisable to consult a cardiologist and ask him to order an electrocardiogram or ultrasound of the heart.

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